

IMPACT OF MOISTURE ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF YARNS UNDER TENSION

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of moisture on the mechanical behavior of yarns, focusing specifically on tensile failure. The objective is to assess how varying levels of moisture affect yarn tensile strength through the application of mathematical models and experimental analysis. The findings are critical for enhancing material quality in the textile industry.

Keywords: moisture, mechanical behavior, tensile strength, elongation, textile materials.

Introduction and literature review

Moisture has a significant effect on the mechanical properties of yarns, especially when they are stretched and broken. The composition of the yarn, the specificity of its structure, and the environmental conditions, for example, the level of humidity, play an important role in these processes. Research shows that moisture can weaken or improve the bond between fibers, which can decrease or increase yarn strength. This paper examines mathematical models and experimental studies describing the effect of moisture content on the mechanical properties of yarns.

The research analyzes the influence of humidity and temperature on the mechanical properties of fibers. Moisture reduces the elasticity of the fibers and reduces their strength [1]. The effect of humidity on the breaking strength of fibers

was studied. The results showed a decrease in fracture strength of approximately 12% in wet environments [2]. It is noted that the mechanical properties of jute fibers at the natural moisture level, especially the tensile strength, are high [3]. Studies on the relationship between moisture and the mechanical properties of yarns analyze the effect of moisture on the structure of fibers and their breaking strength [4]. The developed models describe the deformation of fibers under the influence of moisture, which is used to evaluate the properties of polymer fabrics [5]. The mechanical properties of polyamide fibers under short and long-term moisture conditions were analyzed and a significant effect of hydrolysis was determined [6]. Elongation and mechanical properties of carbon fibers under the influence of moisture were studied. Moisture has been reported as a major factor affecting tensile mechanics [7]. Mechanical properties of hybrid cellulose fibers, including moisture absorption and tensile properties, were analyzed [8]. The relationship between moisture and chemical treatment processes and the mechanical strength of yarns was evaluated [9]. The analysis of moisture and stress processes on cotton fibers, their influence on mechanical properties is described [10].

The main part

The effect of humidity: As the moisture level of the yarn increases, its mechanical properties, including tensile strength and elasticity, also change. In general, the strength of the thread may decrease with increasing humidity.

Theoretical studies

The change in the moisture content of the thread over time is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = k(M_s - M(t)) \quad (1)$$

Here:

- k is the mass transfer coefficient, which depends on the relative speed.

The relative speed v_{nisb} is defined as follows:

$$v_{nisb} = |v_{ip} - v_{bug'}| \quad (2)$$

The mass transfer coefficient k is proportional to the relative velocity:

$$k = k_0 \cdot v_{nisb} \quad (3)$$

Here:

- k_0 is an empirically determined proportionality coefficient.

We put k in the differential equation:

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = k_0 \cdot v_{nisb} (M_s - M(t)) \quad (4)$$

For Ground Thread (v_1):

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = k_0 \cdot |v_1 - v_{bug'}| (M_s - M(t)) \quad (5)$$

For Hairy Tanda Ipi (v_2):

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = k_0 \cdot |v_2 - v_{bug'}| (M_s - M(t)) \quad (6)$$

Equilibrium humidity M_s is a function of air temperature T and relative humidity ϕ :

$$M_s = f(T, \phi) \quad (7)$$

This function is based on the sorption isotherms of the yarn material.

Based on the above, we form general differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dM_1}{dt} = k_0 \cdot |v_1 - v_{bug'}| (f(T, \phi) - M_1(t)) \\ \frac{dM_2}{dt} = k_0 \cdot |v_2 - v_{bug'}| (f(T, \phi) - M_2(t)) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

These differential equations describe the variation of yarn moisture content with time, taking into account yarn velocities, vapor velocities, air temperature, and relative humidity.

To solve these equations analytically, we rewrite the differential equations in such a way that the variable is isolated and find the general solution using the integral. It is a first-order linear differential equation involving the variable and time t . Let's break this down into separate variables: $M_1(t)$

$$\frac{dM_1}{f(T, \phi) - M_1(t)} = k_0 \cdot |v_1 - v_{bug'}| dt \quad (9)$$

It is a first-order linear differential equation involving the variable and time

ttt. Let's break this down into separate variables: $M_1(t)$

$$\int \frac{1}{f(T, \phi) - M_1(t)} dM_1 = \int k_0 \cdot |v_1 - v_{bug'}| dt \quad (10)$$

We solve the integral on the left side:

$$-\ln|f(T, \phi) - M_1(t)| = k_0 \cdot |v_1 - v_{bug'}| \cdot t + C_1 \quad (11)$$

Here is the integration constant. Writing in exponential form, we express: $C_1 M_1(t)$

$$f(T, \phi) - M_1(t) = C_1 e^{k_0 \cdot |v_1 - v_{bug'}| \cdot t} \quad (12)$$

Now we separate: $M_1(t)$

$$M_1(t) = f(T, \phi) - C_1 e^{k_0 \cdot |v_1 - v_{bug'}| \cdot t} \quad (13)$$

Using the initial conditions, we find . For example, $M_1(0) = M_{1,0}$ at $t=0$: C_1

$$M_{1,0} = f(T, \phi) - C_1 \quad (14)$$

$$C_1 = f(T, \phi) - M_{1,0} \quad (15)$$

Final solution:

$$M_1(t) = f(T, \phi) - (f(T, \phi) - M_{1,0}) e^{k_0 \cdot |v_1 - v_{bug'}| \cdot t} \quad (16)$$

Thread Breakage Model: To model the thread breakage probability, we need to relate the breakage probability Breakage to the moisture level $M(t)$.

$$P_{uzilish} = P_0 e^{\alpha(M(t) - M_{kirit})} \quad (17)$$

Here:

- P_0 — initial failure probability in dry state.
- α — coefficient of influence of humidity on interruption.
- $M(t)$ — moisture content of the thread depending on time.
- M_{kirit} — critical moisture level, above which the probability of failure increases.

Modeling Purpose

• **Probability of Interruption by Time:** We calculate the moisture level of the threads at each moment of time and determine the probability of breakage.

• **Modeling for Optimal Steam Velocity:** We model the time variation of the humidity level and the probability of thread breakage for the previously determined optimal steam velocity ($v_{\text{steam}}=1.0-1.5$ m/s).

The probability of breakage with equilibrium moisture is approximately Breakage=0.0116 (or 1.16%). This means that the probability of breaking when the moisture content of the yarn reaches the equilibrium state is slightly increased compared to the dry state, but it is still acceptable.

When yarns absorb moisture, the water molecules in them enter the yarn fibers and change their internal structure. This process has a significant effect on the mechanical strength and hardness of the yarn. Moisture can soften the fibers and increase the elasticity of the yarn, but it also reduces its tensile strength.

When the equilibrium moisture is reached, the yarn moisture content is high, but in equilibrium conditions. The probability of failure at equilibrium moisture calculated above was about 1.16%. This probability is increased compared to the probability of a dry failure, but it is still acceptable.

As the moisture content increases, the tensile strength of the yarn decreases, but a certain level of moisture content, such as the equilibrium moisture content, may be necessary to improve the quality of the fabric during weaving. If the thread is too dry during the knitting process, it becomes brittle and the possibility of breakage increases. Therefore, it is very important to wet the thread optimally - it should not exceed the amount of moisture, and the mechanical strength of the thread should remain sufficient.

Determination of the moisture content at an optimal level, which ensures that the mechanical strength of the threads is maintained and the possibility of breakage is kept to a minimum. The optimal level of moisture is determined based on the mechanical properties of the threads, the effect of moisture on their tensile strength, as well as the technological parameters of the moistening process (Fig. 1).

Critical Moisture Level (M_{crit}): This is the value that the moisture level has

a significant effect on the mechanical strength of the threads and rapidly increases the probability of breakage. We assume that this value can be around 12-15%.

Floor Yarn (Initial Moisture: 10-12%): If moisture is supplied to the ground thread with cold steam, it should be kept at a maximum of 12-13%, as this value is slightly below the critical moisture level, which helps to reduce the possibility of breakage.

Hairy Tanda Yarn (Initial Moisture: 6%): Optimum moisture content for wool yarn should be increased to around 10-11%. This level increases the tensile strength of the thread and ensures the inherent strength of the thread.

Figure 1. Moisture level and probability of failure

Summary

As the moisture level increases, the probability of failure also increases, especially after the critical level (12%). Below the critical moisture level, the probability of failure is relatively low. This means that the optimal moisture content should be kept slightly below the critical level. Ground Thread: Keeping the moisture content between 10-12% is optimal as the chance of breakage is relatively low. Hairy Tanda Yarn: It is recommended to increase the moisture content to around 10-11% as the possibility of breaking becomes minimal at this moisture

level.

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